

PERFORMANCE OF SORGHUM IN MAHARASHTRA: DISTRICT-WISE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Sorghum, is known as the “King of Millets,” as a key staple for food-insecure populations across the semi-arid tropics, it holds significant importance both globally and nationally ranking fifth among cereal crops worldwide and third in India. The present study analyzes the trends in area, production, and productivity of sorghum across ten major districts of Maharashtra and the pattern of market arrivals and prices of Sorghum in the four major APMCs of Maharashtra over a 20-year period (2005–2024). Using time-series data, compound growth rates (CGR) and coefficients of variation (CV) were estimated for two sub-periods: Period I (2004–05 to 2013–14) and Period II (2014–15 to 2023–24), as well as for the overall period. Findings reveal a general decline in area, production, and productivity across most districts during Period I, Parbhani was the only district to record stable growth across all three parameters. In Period II, a trend of negative growth was observed in all districts for the area except Jalna and most of the districts shows positive and stable growth rate for production and productivity and significant at 1 and 5 per cent. Overall, while area and production were negative in all districts and for area all most all the districts is significant at the 1 per cent level, productivity improved in most areas except Nanded and Satara. The CV analysis highlighted Beed emerged as the most unstable district in terms of area variation, with CV increasing from 58.79 per cent in Period I to 67.91 per cent in Period II. Nanded showed extreme instability in production, with CV rising dramatically from 27.85 per cent to 177.28 per cent. Satara, on the other hand, remained the most stable district across all parameters. And there is an inverse relationship between prices and the arrival of Sorghum in the selected market of Maharashtra. Overall, the study highlights significant spatial and temporal variability in sorghum cultivation across Maharashtra. As sorghum crop is traditional crop in the state it is essential for policymakers and researchers to place greater focus on this crop to support its development and sustainability.

Keywords- Sorghum, Seasonal variation, Cyclical variation, Compound growth rates and Coefficients of variation.

Introduction

Sorghum (**Sorghum bicolor**) is a cereal crop belonging to the family Poaceae. It is a hardy, drought-resistant plant that thrives in tropical and subtropical regions. Sorghum is a vital crop in sustainable agriculture due to its resilience to harsh climatic conditions, including drought and poor soil fertility. And one of the main staple foods for the world's poorest and most food-insecure people across the semiarid tropics, so is also known as “The KING OF MILLETS”. It is the fifth most important cereal crops in the world, after wheat, maize, rice, barley whereas ;in India Sorghum is the third cereal crops after rice and wheat.

Globally Sorghum is grown on approximately 40-45 million hectares globally, with an annual production of around 60-65 million metric tons in 2021-22. The leading producers of Sorghum include the United States, India, Nigeria, Sudan, and Mexico. In India area under Sorghum is 4.08 Million Hectares and production 4.74 Million Tonnes with productivity of 1162 Kg /Hectare in 2023-24. The major Sorghum producing States are Maharashtra, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra having highest area and production 1.48 Million Hectares and 1.31 Million Tonnes while Karnataka having highest productivity 1228 Kg /Hectare in 2022-23.

Methodology:

The study was undertaken to examine the growth and instability of sorghum in Maharashtra and for the seasonal variation and cyclical variation the time series data on monthly average prices and arrivals of Sorghum for period from 2005 to 2024 were collected from the APMC'S markets namely Ahilyanagar, Beed, Jalana and Solapur.

Collection of Data:

The study was based on district wise secondary data collected from the website Department of Agriculture, Government of Maharashtra. The data collected for the period of last 20 years, from 2004-05 to 2023-24. Monthly prices and arrival figures of Sorghum were collected monthly wise for last 20 years from four major Agriculture Produce Market Committees (APMCs), specifically chosen for their significant Sorghum arrivals. These APMCs included Ahilyanagar, Beed, Jalana and Solapur. Additionally, the website www.agmarknet.nic.in was utilized to supplement the data collection process.

Analytical Techniques:**Growth Rate Analysis:**

The compound growth rates of area, production, productivity of Sorghum was estimated by using following exponential.

Where, $y = ab^t$ (1)

Y = Area / Production / Productivity.

t = Time Variable.

b = Regression coefficient.

a= Intercept.

The equation will be estimated after transforming (1) as follows,

$\log Y = \log a + t \log b$ (2)

Then the per cent compound growth rates ‘r’ will be computed by using the following formula.

$CGR (r) = \frac{[Antilog (\log b) - 1]}{100} \times 100$(3)

Where,

r = Compound growth rate.

Instability Analysis:

The instability in area, production and productivity was calculated using Coefficient of Variation

$CV\% = \frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$

Estimation of Seasonal variations in prices and arrivals of Sorghum:

Most widely used method of measuring seasonal fluctuations i.e method of moving average was used to calculate seasonal indices. To measure the seasonal variations in prices and arrivals seasonal indices were calculated employing twelve months ratio to moving average method The seasonal indices were calculated by adopting the following steps.

1. Generate a series of 12 months moving totals.
2. Generate a series of 12 months moving averages: A series of 12 months moving averages is generated by dividing 12 months moving totals by 12.
3. Generate a series of centred 12 months moving averages. This step involves taking averages of pairs of two subsequent 12 months moving averages and entering between each pair. There are no corresponding moving averages for the first six and last six months.
4. Express each original value as a percentage of corresponding centered moving average. The percentage of moving average represents indices of seasonal and irregular components combined.

5. The next step involves removing the irregular component.
6. Arrange the percentages of moving averages in the form of monthly arrays.
7. Next, the average index for each month is calculated.
8. These averages are to be adjusted in such a way that their sum becomes 1200. This can be done by working out of correction factor and multiplying the average for each month by this correction factor. The correction factor (K) is worked out as follows:

$$K = \frac{1200}{S}$$

Where, K is correction factor and S is sum of averages indices for 12 months, multiply K with the percentage of moving average for each month to obtain the seasonal indices.

Estimation of cyclical indices of prices and arrivals of Sorghum:

(** and * indicates 1 per cent and 5 per cent level of significance respectively)

The residual method of estimating cyclical movement in time series was used for estimating cyclical indices, after eliminating the seasonal variation and trend components. This is accomplished by dividing (Y_t) by corresponding (S) for time (t) symbolically. These deseasonalized data contain cyclical and irregular components and are plotted against time for examining cyclical behaviour. If there is any existence of cycle, periodicity of cycle is noted.

Results And Discussion:

Compound growth rate of area, production and productivity of Sorghum:

The growth performance of Sorghum across various districts in Maharashtra considering its cultivated area, production, and productivity was thoroughly examined using compound growth rate estimations. The detailed findings of this analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: District wise compound growth rate of Sorghum in Maharashtra.

Districts	Particulars	Period I (2004-05 To 2013-14)	Period II (2014-15 To 2023-24)	Overall Period CGR(%) (2004-05 to 2023-24)
Beed	Area	-3.72*	-11.36	-4.34*
	Production	-6.41	14.02	-3.12
	Productivity	-2.79	17.35**	1.26
Ahilyanagar	Area	-1.98*	-11.11**	-4.45**
	Production	-6.05	-2.12	-3.45
	Productivity	-4.16	10.28	1.25
Dharashiv	Area	-2.21*	-2.79	-5.31*
	Production	-3.31	11.76*	-2.99
	Productivity	-1.13	14.97**	2.44
Jalna	Area	-6.65*	8.20	-3.80*
	Production	-13.91	24.33*	-3.16
	Productivity	-7.76	0.14*	0.67
Nanded	Area	-5.05**	-8.61**	-6.41**
	Production	-5.14	0.10	-6.31*
	Productivity	-0.09	11.08**	-1.44
Pune	Area	-9.07*	-17.28**	-9.41**
	Production	-7.47	-9.09*	-8.03**
	Productivity	1.75	9.89*	1.52
Solapur	Area	-3.75**	-9.65**	-3.64**
	Production	-5.64	0.09	-1.68
	Productivity	-1.47	10.79*	2.19
Satara	Area	-2.77*	-4.22**	-2.34**
	Production	-3.09	-3.12	-2.50**
	Productivity	-0.30	1.15	-0.13
Sangli	Area	0.67	-5.81**	-3.04**
	Production	-7.03	1.95	-1.32
	Productivity	-7.65*	8.24*	1.78
Parbhani	Area	0.15	-9.79*	-5.73**
	Production	1.26	3.82	-4.21*
	Productivity	1.11	15.10**	1.62

From the above Table 1 revealed that the compound growth rates were negative and statistically significant in almost all cases, which gives alarming signals for farmer as well as policy maker.

In Period I, nearly all districts in the Maharashtra experienced a decline in area, production, and productivity and the growth rate of area in most of the district are significant at 5 per cent level. Pune having highest decline in area i.e. -9.07 per cent. Jalna shows highest in decline in production and productivity i.e. -13.91 per cent and -7.76 per cent respectively. However, Prabhani did show stable growth in area with 0.15 per cent, Production with 1.26 per cent and productivity 1.11 per cent.

During Period II it shows fluctuating growth compared to period I. In Period II, a trend of negative growth was observed in all districts for the area except Jalna and most of the districts shows positive and stable growth rate for production and productivity and significant at 1 and 5 per cent. Pune shows highest decline in area and production i.e. 17.28 per cent and -9.09 per cent respectively. Jalna shows all positive growth in area, production, and productivity and highest in area and production i.e. 8.20 per cent and 24.33 per cent respectively. Highest productivity shows in Beed with 17.35 per cent. A better picture of positive and stable growth in productivity is observed in all districts in the Maharashtra in period II.

Over the entire 20-year period, the compound growth rates of area and production were negative in all districts and significant at 1 per cent level, while it observed stable growth in productivity except Nanded and Satara. Highest decline rate in area and production observed in Pune i.e. -9.41 per cent and -8.03 per cent respectively and lowest in decline rate in area observed in satra i.e. -2.34 per cent and in production it is Sangli i.e. -1.32 per cent. A stable growth in productivity is observed in almost all districts in the Maharashtra despite sorghum cultivation area in Maharashtra is decreasing, the stable productivity suggests farmers are adopting advanced technologies, leading to higher yields despite the shrinking acreage.

It indicates that farmers in the Maharashtra were not aware of the importance of the crop. It is, therefore, necessary to concentrate on this crop for increase in acreage through various extension activities by providing new technology along with high yielding varieties. The result and discussion were found almost similar to Shende and Bagde (2018).

Table 2: District wise instability of Sorghum in Maharashtra.

Districts	Particulars	Period I (2004-05 To 2013-14)	Period II (2014-15 To 2023-24)	Overall (2004-05 To 2023-24)
Beed	Area	58.79	67.91	45.53
	Production	25.67	53.29	39.79
	Productivity	18.81	54.52	41.18
Ahilyanagar	Area	8.62	34.64	26.5
	Production	36.46	41.09	41.07
	Productivity	34.68	43.29	39.16
Dharashiv	Area	9.38	27.78	34.62
	Production	20.12	40.58	35.9
	Productivity	18.88	41.10	34.37
Jalna	Area	24.19	34.41	36.44
	Production	43.02	56.24	51.64
	Productivity	33.40	42.94	29.6
Nanded	Area	17.97	32.13	37.83
	Production	27.85	177.28	110.99
	Productivity	18.95	33.62	29.6
Pune	Area	31.65	50.00	52.25
	Production	17.57	40.21	56.64
	Productivity	16.72	38.11	29.6
Solapur	Area	13.91	29.69	23.94
	Production	28.22	35.18	30.02
	Productivity	21.37	34.71	31.16
Satara	Area	12.67	15.37	16.73
	Production	18.67	17.32	21.35
	Productivity	17.02	17.09	16.67
Sangli	Area	8.71	0.20	20.76
	Production	37.46	27.75	33.24
	Productivity	33.23	29.02	32.14
Parbhani	Area	13.78	45.21	37.53
	Production	19.08	47.77	40.75
	Productivity	19.61	40.32	31.51

From the above table 2 it revealed that the highest instability in area is pune (52.25%) and lowest is Satara (16.73%). The highest instability in production is Nanded (110.99%) and lowest is Stara (21.35%). And instability for productivity lies between 16.67 per cent and 41.18 per cent. Further, instability in productivity in relation to instability in area was contributed marginally towards production fluctuation. Overall, the coefficient of variation (CV) of area, production and productivity were Moderate Variability except Nanded and Satra. Nanded shows very high fluctuating in production i.e. (110.99%), while Satra shows relatively

Variability in area, production and productivity of Sorghum in Maharashtra:

The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is a statistical measure of the relative variability expressed as a percentage. It provides insights into the stability or volatility of different aspects of agricultural performance, including area, production, and productivity. Higher CV values indicate greater variability, while lower CV values suggest more stability.

One should not obvious of instability by considering the growth rates only. Because the growth rates would explain only the rate of growth over the period, whereas, instability will judge, whether the growth performance is stable or unstable for the period for the pertinent variable. To facilitate better understanding of the magnitude and pattern of changes in the level of production, cropped area and productivity of sorghum in the major districts of Maharashtra, instability of area, production and productivity of sorghum have been worked out and presented in table 2.

stable in area, production and productivity i.e. 16.73, 21.35 and 16.67 per cent. The coefficient of variation for area under sorghum is compatibly little low to the production and productivity. Further, instability in productivity in relation to instability in area was contributed marginally towards production fluctuation. The result and discussion were found almost similar to Shende and Bagde (2018).

Seasonal and Cyclical variations in Arrivals and Prices of Sorghum Seasonal indices for Sorghum arrival:

In Maharashtra sorghum is typically grown during both the Kharif and the Rabi seasons, but majorly grown in post-rainy season. The sowing of sorghum in post-rainy season started from October and harvested started

from the end of January. The seasonal indices thus calculated are presented in table 3.

Table 3 Seasonal indices for sorghum arrivals in selected markets of Maharashtra.

MONTH	Beed	Ahilyanagar	Jalna	Solapur
JAN	52.61	81.96	37.54	93.65
FEB	86.70	173.08	65.32	100.17
MAR	176.59	137.07	134.41	109.98
APR	183.19	175.50	178.10	120.60
MAY	117.20	100.77	133.49	116.72
JUN	105.54	83.61	118.68	101.04
JUL	80.85	91.83	90.66	94.30
AUG	80.89	79.62	109.36	86.30
SEP	88.13	67.97	119.26	92.91
OCT	79.98	76.40	95.43	84.44
NOV	82.20	81.68	74.30	97.82
DEC	66.11	70.52	59.45	102.07

It is seen from the table 3 that highest arrivals were recorded from the month of March and June in all the selected APMCs, and the lean period for Sorghum arrivals seen from October to January. The peak arrivals were recorded in the month of April in Beed (183.19) followed by Jalna (178.10), Ahilyanagar (175.50) and Solapur (120.60) and lowest arrivals seen in October. Similar findings have been reported by (Rao and Valvan, 2005).

Seasonal Indices for Sorghum prices:

To analyse the long-term seasonal variations in sorghum prices in the selected markets, seasonal indices were computed using the 12-month moving average method. The seasonal indices of monthly sorghum prices in these markets are comprehensively presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Seasonal indices for sorghum prices in selected markets of Maharashtra.

MONTH	Beed	Ahilyanagar	Solapur	Jalna
JAN	104.67	112.06	104.71	104.63
FEB	104.09	101.62	92.00	101.43
MAR	100.64	103.42	94.62	99.14
APR	97.91	99.11	91.25	96.06
MAY	96.94	94.80	91.95	96.59
JUN	96.41	88.68	93.08	96.34
JUL	99.12	110.64	102.38	98.86
AUG	96.27	92.25	96.49	98.68
SEP	95.63	85.11	101.61	94.37
OCT	94.02	86.11	105.34	98.55
NOV	105.47	108.82	109.11	107.43
DEC	108.84	117.39	117.11	107.91

It can be observed from the table 4 that prices were increases from the month of November to February in all the selected APMCs. The highest prices were observed in the month of December in Beed (108.84), Ahilyanagar (117.39), Solapur (117.11) and Jalna (107.91). The prices increase largely due to the seasonal shortage of Sorghum during these

months. The result of present findings are in close confirming with the result reported by (Rao and Valvan, 2005).

Cyclical indices for arrival of Sorghum:

The year-to-year fluctuations in arrivals of Red Chilli were worked out and presented in the table 5.

Table 5. Cyclical indices for sorghum arrivals in selected markets of Maharashtra

YEAR	Beed	Ahilyanagar	Jalna	Solapur
2005	98.80	101.08	165.79	105.90
2006	113.55	44.92	134.25	114.73
2007	114.74	132.41	113.12	110.84
2008	154.04	129.06	92.53	108.99
2009	107.88	138.21	114.16	108.66
2010	64.36	192.45	177.75	91.23
2011	57.61	74.06	61.43	71.47
2012	61.51	74.57	69.88	88.07
2013	94.51	73.18	69.94	78.29
2014	82.28	102.26	63.80	65.66

2015	111.20	184.40	61.96	69.29
2016	125.29	140.52	59.21	55.21
2017	138.31	110.84	134.53	74.10
2018	79.25	54.09	125.89	81.74
2019	22.64	29.82	66.96	79.35
2020	69.94	34.26	58.59	133.53
2021	144.41	59.59	93.44	166.21
2022	100.43	86.73	77.32	127.43
2023	123.17	83.39	81.72	120.47
2024	139.07	154.15	177.72	148.84

It is evident from the table 5, some years exhibit higher indices across most districts i.e. (2005, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2017 and 2024), suggesting periods of higher arrivals while the lower arrivals are seen in (2010, 2011, 2012, 2019 and 2020). In Beed highest arrival seen in 2008 (154.04) and the lowest in 2019 (22.64). High arrivals occurred for Beed in 2006-9, 2016-17, 2023-24, while low arrivals were seen in 2010-14 and 2018-20. In Ahilyanagar highest arrivals seen in 2010 (192.45) and lowest 2019 (29.82). High arrivals occurred for Ahilyanagar in 2007-10, 2015-17 and 2024 while low arrivals seen in 2006, 2011-13 and 2018-21. In Jalna highest arrival seen in 2024 (177.72) and lowest in 2020 (58.59). High arrivals seen for Jalna in 2005-07, 2009-10, 2017-18 and 2024, while low

arrivals observed in 2008, 2011-16 and 2019-20. In Solapur highest arrival seen in 2024 (148.84) and lowest in 2016 (55.21). High arrivals seen in 2006-09 and 2020-24, while low arrivals observed from 2011 to 2019. It is also observed that, a well defined cycle could not be observed regarding the arrivals in selected markets of Maharashtra.

Cyclical indices for sorghum prices:

To understand the patterns in sorghum prices, this study analyzes the cyclical price indices of sorghum across four major districts in Maharashtra to gain deeper insights into pricing patterns. These indices highlight annual trends, revealing seasonal fluctuations and market variations, as presented in the table 6.

Table 6 Cyclical indices for sorghum prices in selected markets of Maharashtra

YEAR	Beed	Ahilyanagar	Solapur	Jalna
2005	95.80	92.24	105.12	78.40
2006	113.55	81.24	80.96	73.82
2007	114.74	90.68	105.99	110.39
2008	154.04	110.38	110.55	100.47
2009	107.88	105.37	72.65	79.31
2010	64.36	135.22	89.07	96.83
2011	57.61	126.05	163.08	155.80
2012	61.51	104.15	121.56	118.73
2013	94.51	63.26	92.80	99.52
2014	82.28	93.84	100.99	96.81
2015	111.20	82.56	97.15	100.27
2016	125.29	83.88	91.15	105.87
2017	138.31	110.92	83.95	90.01
2018	79.25	108.61	87.68	87.65
2019	22.64	98.40	82.99	123.16
2020	69.94	113.05	79.21	96.95
2021	144.41	101.83	104.04	70.21
2022	100.43	94.90	93.67	91.71
2023	123.17	117.37	141.78	132.19
2024	139.07	86.03	95.60	91.89

It is evident from the table 6, that cyclical indices exhibit higher indices in the selected APMCs during the years (e.g., 2008, 2011, 2021, 2023), suggesting periods of higher prices. Beed market Shows significant fluctuations with high indices in 2007 (114.74), 2008 (154.04), 2021 (144.41) and 2023 (123.17) while the lowest indices appear in 2012 (61.51) and 2019 (22.64). In Ahilyanagar market it shows relatively stable indices with peak in 2008 (110.38), 2011 (126.05), and 2023 (117.37) and lowest indices is in 2013 (63.26) and 2015 (82.56). The Solapur experiences peak in 2011 (163.08) and 2023 (141.78) and lowest indices in 2009 (72.65) and 2020 (79.21). In Jalna shows high indices in 2011 (155.80) and 2023 (132.19) and lowest indices in 2005 (78.40) and 2006 (73.82). In the year 2008 and 2023 shows higher indices in most of APMCs of Maharashtra and also show lower indices in 2013 and 2018 in all the district. There are consistent patterns of peaks and troughs in

the indices, reflecting seasonal trends and market conditions. The periodic peaks and troughs might be due to factors like crop yield variations, market demand, and external economic conditions. It is also observed that, a well defined cycle could not be observed the in selected markets of Maharashtra.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the present study that , the compound growth rates of area and production were negative in all districts and for area all most all the districts is significant at the 1 per cent level, while it observed positive in productivity expect Nanded and Satara. A positive growth in productivity is observed in almost all districts in the Maharashtra. The coefficient of variation (CV%) of area, production and productivity were Moderate Variability except Nanded and Satra. Nanded shows very high fluctuating in production i.e. (110.99%), while Satra shows relatively

stable in area, production and productivity i.e. 16.73, 21.35 and 16.67 per cent. Further, instability in productivity in relation to instability in area was contributed marginally towards production fluctuation.

The peak period of arrivals of Sorghum in the selected markets is March to June. Whereas July to January is the lean period of arrivals of Sorghum in the selected markets. The prices of Sorghum were higher from the month of November to February in selected markets. In case of cyclical indices, a well-defined cycle could not be observed regarding arrivals and prices in selected markets of Maharashtra. The study revealed that the pattern of arrivals and prices was directly supported in decision-making by the farmers and various intermediaries.

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